

Multi-source data integration of Lower Cretaceous units with geothermal potential in Lisbon region, Portugal, to support geological modelling

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The Lisbon region, the urban area with the highest population density and energy demand in Portugal, presents a favourable geological environment for geothermal purposes. The objective of this study was to integrate all the information known from different sources to support the construction of a geological model of the Lower Cretaceous units, which reveal the geothermal potential. The methodology developed in this study allows the integration of data from different sources into a single georeferenced and refined database. The eastern sector of the city of Lisbon, identified as the most promising area for geothermal applications, shows a lack of geological information at depth. However, a future junction of existing seismic profiles with the data obtained in the present study could resolve this issue.

La région de Lisbonne, zone urbaine avec la densité de population et la demande d'énergie, les plus élevées du Portugal, offre un environnement géologique favorable du point de vue énergie géothermique. Le but de cette étude fut d'intégrer l'ensemble des informations disponibles et venant de différentes sources pour soutenir la création d'un modèle géologique rapporté aux horizons du Crétacé inférieur qui représentent un potentiel géothermique certain. La méthode développée dans cette étude permet d'intégrer les données d'origines diverses en une base de données unique, géo référencée et épurée. Le secteur oriental de la ville de Lisbonne, identifié comme le plus prometteur au niveau applications géothermales est assorti d'un défaut de données géologiques profondes. Cependant, la future adjonction de profils sismiques existants aux données obtenues lors de cette étude, serait à même de résoudre ce défaut.

La región de Lisboa es la zona urbana con mayor densidad de población y demanda de energía en Portugal, presenta un entorno geológico favorable para la geotermia. El objetivo de este estudio fue integrar toda la información conocida de diferentes fuentes, para apoyar la construcción de un modelo geológico de las unidades del Cretácico Inferior, que revela el potencial geotérmico. La metodología desarrollada en este estudio permite la integración de datos de diferentes fuentes en una sola base de datos georeferenciada y filtrada. La zona este de Lisboa, identificada como la zona más prometedora para aplicaciones geotérmicas, muestra una falta de información geológica de profundidad. Sin embargo, una futura unión de perfiles sísmicos existentes con los datos obtenidos en el presente estudio podría resolver este problema.

1. Introduction

It is widely known that large sedimentary basins are favourable for the existence of deep aquifers which, with a medium or even smaller geothermal gradient, are also susceptible to be exploited as low-enthalpy geothermal reservoirs. The Lisbon region, located in the western Meso-Cenozoic sedimentary basin (Rassmussen *et al.*, 1998; Dias *et al.*, 2013) presents deep aquifers in sedimentary formations, very favourable for geothermal purposes (Correia *et al.*, 2002; Marrero-Diaz *et al.*, 2015). Within the lithostratigraphic units identified in the Lisbon region, the geothermal potential of

the Lower Cretaceous stands out with its relatively low mineralised water (salinity <1 g/l) and with a temperature of 50 °C at 1,500 m depth. These units were already being exploited in the 1990s for geothermal purposes in two concrete cases (Carvalho & Cardoso, 1994).

The main objective of the present study was to obtain a methodology to support the construction of three-dimensional geological models aiming to estimate representative surfaces of the lithostratigraphic units of the Early Cretaceous in order to infer their geometry in the Lisbon region. For this purpose, all known information from various sources – geology, hydrogeology and geophysics – was integrated with the intent of filling the lack of data in depth and identifying the most promising sites for geothermal purposes.

The region of Lisbon, with approximately

960 km², is the urban area with the highest population density in Portugal (corresponding to about 19 % of the inhabitants of the country), which results in a strong demand for energy; in this way, geothermal energy could be seen as a possible environment-friendly energy source in this area.

2. Study area

From a tectonic-sedimentary point of view, the Lisbon region is part of the southern sector of the Western Meso-Cenozoic border, with formations that belong to the Lusitanian Basin, partially overlain by Cenozoic sediments of the Baixo Tejo Basin (Figure 1). The Lusitanian Basin, deposited in a tectonic pit originated by the tilting of the Hercynian Massif, has been constituted by a >3 km thick normal sequence of sediments since the Triassic until today

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(Rasmussen *et al.*, 1998). The Baixo Tejo Basin represents a normal sedimentary sequence with a thickness of about 1,500 m from the Paleogene until today (Dias *et al.*, 2013).

Due to the vast number of geological formations identified in the Lisbon region, only 8 lithostratigraphic units were chosen to simplify and group (Table 1).

From all the lithostratigraphic units identified, Lower Cretaceous units, namely the *Grés de Almagem* and *Barremian-Berriasian* units (Table 1), have the greatest interest considering their geothermal potential (Marrero-Diaz *et al.*, 2015). The *Grés de Almagem* lithostratigraphic unit is mainly constituted of ferruginous sandstones, pellets and conglomerates, interbedded with limestones and calcareous marls (Rey, 1993; LNEG, 2011). Generally, it is a sequence of sandstones, carbonates and sandstones again that has an average thickness in the order of 100 m, with relatively significant lateral variations. The *Barremian-Berriasian* unit groups several sedimentary formations composed essentially of limestones, marls, sandstones and pellets, with an average thickness of 200 m (LNEG, 1993).

According to Marrero-Diaz *et al.* (2015) and references therein, the *Grés de Almagem* unit behaves as a multi-layered semi-confined, often artesian, dual-porosity aquifer with coexisting intergranular and fracture circulation and effective porosity between 7 and 18 %, allowing exploration flow rates up to 50 l/s. The statistical study of 76 groundwater wells exploiting *Grés de Almagem* unit in the Lisbon region shows thicknesses between 60 m and 229 m with a mean value of 135 m, and transmissivities between 1 and 386 m²/d with a mean of 26 m²/d.

3. Multi-source data integration

3.1. Pre-processing

In an initial phase, a survey and selection of all the geological, hydrogeological and geophysical information available in the Lisbon region was carried out, from which the data summarised in Table 2 was selected.

3.2. Processing

The second phase consisted of the organisation and integration of previously selected data into a single georeferenced database using the ArcGIS ESRI platform, through the steps described below:

Figure 1: Geological map of the study area, with the study area limit in red, obtained from the junction of Sheets 34A, 34B, 34C and 34D of the Geological Map of Portugal at 1:50,000 scale (LNEG, 1993, 2011, 1999, 2006). Coordinate system Lisboa Hayford Gauss IGeoE used here and in all maps below.

Table 1: Lithostratigraphic units grouped in the study area and acronyms of the formations considered from Sheets 34A, 34B, 34C and 34D of the Geological Map of Portugal at 1:50,000 scale (LNEG, 1993, 2011, 1999, 2006).

Unit (Age)	Sheet	Acronyms
Miocene (Idem)	34A	$M^3l + M^3m$
	34B e 34D	$M_{Mv} + M_{BP} + M_{CR} + M_{QC} + M_{Xa} + M_{Gr} + M_{Mu} + M_{VC} + M_{Es} + M_{Ec} + M_{Ft} + M_{QB} + M_{CV} + M_{Pm} + M_{Pr}$
	34C	$M^e_{III} + M^i_{II} + M^i_I$
Paleogene (Idem)	34A	\emptyset
	34B e 34D	\emptyset_{Bf}
	34C	\emptyset
LVC - SMSM Lisbon Volcanic Complex – Subvolcanic Massif of Sintra-Mafra (Santonian)	34A and 34C	β^1
	34B and 34D	B
Bica (Turonian)	34A and 34C	C^3_C
	34B and 34D	$C^2_{Bf} + C^2_{Fq}$
Caneças (Cenomanian – Upper Albian)	34A and 34C	C^2_{AC}
	34B	C^2_{GC}
	34D	C^2_{Cn}
Grés de Almagem (Lower Albian – Upper Barremian)	34A and 34C	$C^1_{AS} + C^1_A + C^1_{Ba}$
	34B	$C^1_{Ro} + C^1_G + C^1_{Re}$
Barremian-Berriasian (Idem)	34A	$C^1_{Hba} + C^1_{Hc} + C^1_{Ht} + C^1_V + C^1_{Be}$
	34B	$C^1_{Vl} + C^1_{Sc} + C^1_{RR} + C^1_{Se}$
	34C	$C^1_{Hba} + C^1_H + C^1_V + C^1_{Be}$
Upper Jurassic (Idem)	34A, 34B and 34C	$J^3_{Ab} + J^3_{Am} + J^3_{So} + J^3_{Ar} + J^3_{So} + J^3_{Fr}$

Figure 2: Grés de Almagem points before (left) and after (right) the refinement of boundaries.

Figure 3: Barremian-Berriasian points before (left) and after (right) the refinement of boundaries.

Table 2: Bibliographic summary of selected data.

Source kind	Type of data	Data format	Data specifications	Issuing organisation
Geological	Sheets 34-A, 34-B, 34-C and 34-D of the Geological Map of Portugal at 1:50,000 scale	Digital (vector)	Boundaries of lithostratigraphic units and tectonic structures (faults)	National Laboratory of Energy and Geology (LNEG)
Hydrogeological	Groundwater wells reports	Printed (paper) and digital (pdf)	251 Logs from groundwater wells: lithostratigraphic sequence, static and dynamic piezometric levels, volumetric flow rates, water chemistry	LNEG; Portuguese Environment Agency (APA)
Geophysical	Reflection seismic profiles: AR12-81; AR16-81; AR17B-81; AR28.	Printed (paper) and digital (vector)	Position of reflectors indicating the lithological changes related to the tops of lithostratigraphic units	National Entity for the Fuel Market (ENMC)

3.2.1. Geological data integration

The geological data integrated in the database belong to the geological mapping of Portugal at 1:50,000 scale (Table 2). This data was analysed, interpreted and treated using the ArcGIS ESRI platform and various automated ArcToolbox tools.

Conversion of the polygons of lithostratigraphic units into points

The respective cartographic boundaries of the Grés de Almagem and Barremian-Berriasian units were unified and exported as polygons, which were later subdivided into points. Longitude (x) and latitude (y) in the Lisboa Hayford Gauss IGeoE system were assigned to each point thus obtained,

and, finally, the elevation (z) was also assigned, based on the digital global elevation model (Aster GDEM) with approximately 30 m of spatial resolution.

Refinement of boundaries

In order to identify correspondence points with top and bottom of the lithostratigraphic units, a new field, desig-

Figure 4: Location of groundwater wells with information from the top and bottom of the various units in the study area.

Figure 5: Location of seismic profiles in the study area.

nated as horizon, was added to the georeferenced database obtained from the previous steps. The coding assigned was 1 for the top, and 2 for the bottom.

There are points that do not correspond with the boundaries of top or bottom of the lithostratigraphic units; to solve this incongruence a refinement of the boundaries was manually performed through the ArcGIS ESRI platform, removing less representative points from the georeferenced database, for example, those coincident with contacts with volcanic extrusives or Holocene alluvial deposits. *Figures 2 and 3* show *Grés de Almargem* and *Barremian-Berriasian* points before and after their refinement.

3.2.2. Hydrogeological data integration

For the present study, more than 500 reports of groundwater wells were consulted and analysed in the study area. After a critical review of each report, based on the geological and hydrogeological knowledge of the surrounding area, 251 wells were considered reliable and interesting for the present study (*Figure 4*).

A geological correspondence was proposed between the lithology crossed by the groundwater wells and the top and bottom of the lithostratigraphic units under study, as well as of the other units present in the region (*Table 1*). It should be noted that errors may exist in the proposed geological correspondence, due to the repetition of lithological sequences and the existence of

asynchronous formations or lateral variations. Thus, the presented selection may be improved in the future with the introduction of new knowledge.

Analogously to the geological data integration described previously, codification (1 - top; 2 - bottom) was also assigned to each limit. Additionally, codes 0.5 and 1.5, corresponding to the top and base of the groundwater well, were assigned and denominated "Relative top" and "Minimum bottom", respectively. These new horizons force the model to incorporate the information from the wells, but it should be noted that they are not real boundaries.

3.2.3. Geophysical data integration

Multiple 2D seismic reflection profiles acquired for hydrocarbon prospection in the northern zone of the Lisbon region are available (Rasmussen *et al.*, 1998; Carvalho *et al.*, 2005). However, only 4 reflection seismic profiles are within the study area (*Figure 5*). These seismic profiles were acquired by Veritas in 1963 (AR-28 profile) and by the company Petróleos de Portugal (Petrogal) in 1981 (AR12-81, AR16-81 and AR17B-81 profiles) and initially interpreted by Walker (1983).

Interpretation of the seismic profiles

The interpretation started with the seismic to well tie using well data in the study area and also using previously established seismic-stratigraphy packages identified by other authors in other seismic profiles outside the study area (Carvalho *et al.*, 2005; 2011) that intersect the profiles used in this study. Afterwards, the interpretation proceeded by checking the intersections between each seismic profile and using geological surface information such as geological contacts, faults, etc. Available gravimetric and magnetic data (Carvalho *et al.*, 2011) was also used in the interpretation, which allowed the identification of salt domes, igneous structures and the pre-Mesozoic basement.

Analysis of seismic profiles

Resolution of the seismic information is a crucial parameter for correct analysis of the seismic profiles. Considering an average propagation velocity of the P-waves of 2,500 m/s (corresponding to the homogenisation velocity identified in the considered profiles) and a frequency of 10 Hz, an average vertical resolution of 60 m was obtained.

Strong lithological subsurface contrasts

are traduced in the seismic profiles by a strong reflector. However, chronological contacts do not always correspond to strong reflectors if the chronological boundary represents a continuous depositional episode and/or does not correspond to a sharp lithological boundary (Carvalho *et al.*, 2005). To complement and calibrate this information, tops of the horizons of the *Grés de Almargem* and *Barremian-Berriasian* units (and of the other units present in the region) were also represented in the seismic profiles (Figure 6). These horizon tops were obtained from intersecting seismic profiles previously reprocessed and reinterpreted by Carvalho *et al.* (2005; 2011) and from nearby groundwater wells (considering a buffer of 200 m between the wells and the seismic profiles).

Since the vertical scale of the seismic profiles corresponds to the traditional two-way travel time of the reflected waves, this last task involved the depth-time conversion of the groundwater well information. Due to the lack of check-shots and/or velocity logs in the wells that would allow the accurate knowledge of propagation velocities, the adopted criterion was to consider a homogenisation velocity of 2,500 m/s above the seismic datum (0 milliseconds – corresponding to approximately 150 m depth) and different velocities below 0 milliseconds obtained through the use of well data (Carvalho *et al.* 2005).

Next, a preliminary structural interpretation was performed, and several probable faults were identified, some of them with no surface correspondence in the geological maps of the study zone (Figure 6), though most of the major faults that were identified could be matched in the geological surface maps.

Finally, the top horizons of *Grés de Almargem* and *Barremian-Berriasian* units in time were depth-converted using seismic velocities obtained from well data outside the study area for geological units similar to those found inside the region of interest.

3.3. Database enhancement

Finally, the database was refined, creating a single file using Microsoft Office Excel. Each point from different sources has associated coordinates of x, y and z, and horizon code (1 - top, 2 - bottom, 0.5 - relative top, 1.5 - minimum bottom). Thereafter a selection of the most representative data concerning the top of *Grés de Almargem* and *Barremian-Berriasian* units was performed (Table 3).

This database, constituted by 6,035 points from the diverse data sources considered,

Figure 6: Reinterpretation of the reflection seismic profile AR16-81 showing interpreted probable faults and top horizons corresponding to the distinct lithostratigraphic units.

Figure 7: Location of top and bottom points (grouped by horizons) obtained from the geological (C: cartography), hydrogeological (B: boreholes) and geophysical (S: seismic) data.

Table 3: Enhanced database summary.

Source	Type of data	Number of points corresponding to the top horizon of the Lower Cretaceous units
Geological	Geological mapping	5,897
Hydrogeological	Reports of wells	89
Geophysical	Reflection seismic profiles	49

is the potential input for the future three-dimensional geological modelling of the area (Figure 7).

4. Discussion and conclusion

This study has shown a methodology for integrating data from different sources into a single georeferenced database,

which will allow the future construction of a three-dimensional geological model of the Lower Cretaceous units in the Lisbon region. Figure 8 presents a flowchart with the phases of the work.

In the eastern part of the study area, where a strongly demand for energy exists and predictably Lower Cretaceous units are deeper (and thus a higher temperature

Figure 8: Flowchart showing the distinct phases of the work.

of groundwater is expected), there is still a scarce amount of data (Figure 7). Groundwater wells in this sector usually exploit shallower formations, namely the Miocene and Paleogene units, and there are no seismic profiles. However, seismic profiles previously reprocessed and reinterpreted by Carvalho *et al.* (2005; 2011) exist at Tagus

estuary. Therefore, in order to complete the gaps, the next step would be a junction of those profiles with the data obtained in the present study.

Finally, it is important to note the dynamic feature of this methodology, which in the future may be improved with new data and adopted for other geosciences

applications besides geothermal purposes (e.g. structural geology, hydrogeology, CO₂ storage, etc.).

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